

Effects of chronic exposure to microplastics of different polymer types on early life stages of sea trout *Salmo trutta*

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Effects of microplastics (MPs) on sea trout embryos and larvae were assessed.
- Exposure to MPs of any polymer type did not affect embryos hatching success or rate.
- Larvae survival, growth and frequency of cytotoxic endpoints were not affected.
- Larvae exhibited increased frequency of genotoxic endpoints after exposure to MPs.
- Cortisol was detected in larvae exposed to polystyrene.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the present study was to determine the effect of a long-term (113 days) exposure to microplastics on the development and induction of endocrine, geno- and cytotoxic responses in early life stages of sea trout *Salmo trutta*. Microplastic particles (3000 µm) of three most commonly mass-produced polymers (polystyrene - PS, polyethylene terephthalate - PET and polyethylene - PE) were applied in environmentally realistic concentrations (0.1% of sediment dry weight) in a laboratory experiment imitating the natural environment, typical for sea trout spawning grounds. The exposure of the sea trout, from fertilized eggs to mobile yolk-sac larvae, to microplastics did not affect the hatching success (the survival of embryos), hatching rate and the incubation period. Microplastics of any tested polymer type also had no adverse effect on the larvae survival, growth rate and the rate of yolk sack absorption. Similarly, no changes in frequencies of detected cytotoxicity endpoints compared to the control group were recorded. Exposure to polymer particles induced however the formation of genotoxicity endpoints (nuclear buds, micronuclei and blebbed nuclei cells). The level of total genotoxicity (Σ Gentox) in fish larvae erythrocytes increased significantly in the following sequence: PS > PET > PE. No significant changes in the whole body corticosterone, dehydrocorticosterone and cortisone concentrations due to exposure to microplastics were recorded, while cortisol was detected in larvae exposed to PS. Our results show that long-term, non-ingestion related exposure to microplastics does not affect development of *S. trutta* early life stages but may lead to genotoxic responses. PS seems to be the most hazardous among all polymers studied. This is the first study demonstrating non-ingestion related toxicity of microplastics to the early life stages of fish.

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1. Introduction

The global plastic production has increased dramatically in the last decades and it has been estimated to reach 359 million tons in 2018 (Plastics Europe, 2019). Due to inappropriate or insufficient management practices, urban or terrestrial run-offs, incidental pollution or littering, large proportion of the plastic produced each year ends up in the aquatic environments. It is well documented that plastic is by far the most common component of marine litter (e.g., Galil et al., 1995; Galgani et al., 1995, 2000; Ramirez-Llodra et al., 2013; Topçu et al., 2013; Thiel et al., 2013; Auta et al., 2017). Microplastics (MPs) – usually defined as particles or fibres within a size range of 1–5000 μm (Hidalgo-Ruz et al., 2012) (but according to the recent recommendations consistent with the SI nomenclature defined as items in the size range of 1 to <1000 μm , while the range 1 to <10 mm refers to mesoplastics (Hartmann et al., 2019)) are the predominant component of plastic debris, widespread in all marine habitats (e.g. Browne et al., 2011; Van Cauwenberghe et al., 2015; Auta et al., 2017; Zhao et al., 2018; Thompson, 2015 and references therein; Lusher, 2015 and references therein). They are nowadays regarded as a persistent environmental pollutant (Worm et al., 2017) and one of the main environmental issues of a global concern (EC MSFD, 2008; Andrady, 2011). Although, freshwater bodies such as lakes, streams and rivers, and terrestrial environments are considered to be the transport pathways of plastics from land-based sources to the sea, their plastic pollution is still relatively poorly recognized. However, the rapidly growing number of studies focused on freshwater, especially riverine systems, provides an evidence on a large scale of plastic pollution in these environments (Lechner et al., 2014; Wagner et al., 2014; Eerkes-Medrano et al., 2015; Horton et al., 2017a, 2017b; van Emmerik and Schwarz, 2020; Triebkorn et al., 2019). Sediments of freshwater bodies, similarly to marine bottoms, are considered MPs sinks (Wagner et al., 2014; Rodrigues et al., 2018; Li et al., 2020).

Ubiquitous occurrence of MPs and their small dimensions promote their interactions with aquatic organisms (Wright et al., 2013). Ingestion is the most common type of this interaction. MPs are frequently found in digestive tracts of various organisms, including fish from freshwater, estuarine and marine environments (Hoss and Settle, 1990; Sanchez et al., 2014; Lima et al., 2016; Rummel et al., 2016; Silva-Cavalcanti et al., 2017; Steer et al., 2017). There are numerous examples of a lack of ingestion-related adverse effects of MPs on fish growth (Mazurais et al., 2015; Jovanović et al., 2018), hatching rate (Pitt et al., 2018), survival (Pitt et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2017), or oxidative processes (Oliveira et al., 2013). On the other hand, MPs are known to cause physical harm (Pedà et al., 2016; Jin et al., 2018; Lei et al., 2018) and/or blockage of digestive tracts when ingested (Wright et al., 2013) or other negative effects related mainly to leaching of hazardous substances associated with the plastic materials. The latter effects may be caused by (1) the basic chemical composition of the plastic material, i.e., unreacted residual monomers or polymerization impurities (Halden, 2010; Lithner et al., 2011); (2) the potential additives from the manufacturing process e.g., flame retardants, stabilizers, antioxidants or plasticizers (Teuten et al., 2009; Hermabessiere et al., 2017; León et al., 2019); and (3) the chemicals which may be sorbed from the surrounding environment, mainly persistent organic pollutants (Teuten et al., 2007; Rochman et al., 2013b; Bakir et al., 2014). Thus, microplastic particles have the potential to combine the physical and chemical stressors (Rochman, 2015) and therefore, may influence a wide range of properties at various levels of biological organization.

The growing concerns about the environmental consequences of plastic pollution are reflected in increasing number of studies examining potential impacts of MPs on various aquatic biota. The majority of these studies (44%, including field and experimental research) are focused on fish (de Sá et al., 2018). According to the results of experimental research exposure of fish to MPs may lead to mortality (Mazurais et al., 2015; Lei et al., 2018; Naidoo and Glassom, 2019), induction of

oxidative stress (Greven et al., 2016; Lu et al., 2016; Chen et al., 2017; Ding et al., 2018), induction of neurotoxicity (Ding et al., 2018), altered growth rate (Naidoo and Glassom, 2019), altered gene expression in liver (Vtg I, Chg H and ER α) or in brain (ftz-f1, GnRH, 11 β -hsd2 and tph2) (Rochman et al., 2014a; Karami et al., 2016), changes in blood biochemical parameters (Hamed et al., 2019) or in liver histopathology, induction of liver inflammation (Rochman et al., 2013a; Lu et al., 2016) or modulation of the impact of other pollutants (Oliveira et al., 2013; Karami et al., 2016; Haghi and Banaee, 2017). Surprisingly, the majority of these studies apply to adults or juveniles, while research on the early life stages is lacking. Although embryos are known of having high levels of cellular defenses and thus being able to buffer stress or produce alternative developmental phenotypes (Hamdoun and Epel, 2007), it is well documented that their exposure to some contaminants may cause developmental alterations and consequently may lead to negative developmental effects (Von Westernhagen, 1988; Holm et al., 2005; Lema et al., 2007). The survival and rapid growth of early developmental stages is determinant for the population abundance and fitness (Leggett and Deblois, 1994; Houde, 1997). Especially the yolk-sac stage is considered to be the most sensitive one in fish development process, since any factors affecting its duration might influence the population recruitment (Von Westernhagen, 1988).

Fish early life stages may be exposed to both, MPs laying at the bottom where the spawning period often takes place and in the water column where larvae actively swim after hatching. The available data on the responses of fish early life stages to MPs pollution is, however, limited to the model species – zebrafish *Danio rerio* and the European sea bass *Dicentrarchus labrax*. It was shown that nanoplastics (51 nm) penetrated the chorion of embryos (Pitt et al., 2018) while microplastics (17–45 μm) were ingested by exogenously feeding larvae (Mazurais et al., 2015; Chen et al., 2017; Karami et al., 2017; LeMoine et al., 2018).

Large MPs (1–5 mm, EC MSFD, 2013) recorded both in marine and freshwater environments (Eerkes-Medrano et al., 2015 and references therein; Van Cauwenberghe et al., 2015 and references therein; Horton et al., 2017a) are less likely to be ingested by aquatic organisms but are the potential source of hazardous substances. Fish embryos and yolk-sac larvae do not feed exogenously, thus generally are not vulnerable to ingestion of plastic particles, but are potentially exposed to MPs per se and their leaching products. Unfortunately, the knowledge concerning the non-dietary exposure of early life stages of aquatic fauna to microplastics is insufficient. So far only two studies attempted to determine the non-dietary related toxicity of microplastics. Nobre et al. (2015) and Gandara e Silva et al. (2016) have shown that even short-term (24–48 h) exposure to virgin MPs (polyethylene or polypropylene) and pellets collected from the beach, negatively affected the development of invertebrate embryos, probably due to leaching of additives and adsorbed pollutants. Unfortunately, these authors have used high MPs concentrations (50–250 ml^{-1}) exceeding those typically noted in the environment. Rochman and Boxall (2014) stressed that when trying to understand how plastic debris may impact organisms it is critical to measure the effects at environmentally relevant concentrations and under environmentally relevant exposure conditions. As such, the objective of the present study was to find out if environmentally realistic concentrations of large microplastics (3000 μm) of three different polymer types affect the survival, hatching and growth rate of sea trout *Salmo trutta* (Linnaeus 1758) exposed for 113 days from fertilized embryos to mobile, endogenously feeding larval stage. In addition, concentrations of corticosteroid hormones as well as geno- and cytotoxicity endpoints were determined in larvae to investigate if this chronic exposure to MPs may induce the stress responses. Sea trout is a widely distributed in the northern hemisphere and economically important anadromous salmonid fish species (Jonsson and Jonsson, 2011; FAO, 2012) characterized by a comparatively long embryonic and larval development. To our best knowledge, present study is the first that investigates the effect of a long-term (almost 4-month long) exposure of the early, endogenously feeding life stages of fish to

MPs. Moreover, the effects of MPs on geno- and cytotoxic endpoints assessed using the nuclear abnormalities assay in endogenously feeding fish larvae as well as on corticosteroid response in fish have never been investigated earlier. It must be also stressed that our laboratory experimental setting imitated as much as possible the natural environment typical for sea trout spawning grounds.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Animal maintenance and experimental setup

Salmo trutta embryos obtained thanks to collaboration with the Polish Angling Association, were randomly collected 4 h after fertilization from 19 females spawning in the Stupia river (northern Poland) in December 2018. After transportation to the laboratory, eggs were placed in four specially designed incubators (40 × 20 × 12 cm) made of perforated (perforations 2 mm in diameter) stainless steel. The bottom of each incubator was covered with a layer of gravel particles (diameter ~ 3000 µm, 700 g dry wt. per incubator) imitating the stream bottom typical for sea trout spawning grounds. Each incubator was submerged in a separate glass tank (50 × 35 × 30 cm, V = 50 l) supplied by its own (separated from other systems to avoid mixing of water) recirculation system (~250 l each) pumping water at the average rate of 4.8 l min⁻¹. Each system was equipped with a mechanical and biological filter, a cooling unit (Titan 4000, Aqua Medic, Germany) that maintained the water temperature at the constant level and diaphragm compressor (AT-40, Akwatech, Poland) constantly oxygenating the water. Four hundred eggs were placed randomly at the bottom of each incubator. The water flow through the tanks and perforated incubators ensured that the embryos were constantly and vigorously washed with fresh and oxygenated water. The temperature in each tank was monitored continuously by Hobo loggers UA-001-08 (Onset, USA), with a resolution frequency of 10 min. The oxygen concentration was measured every two days using HQ40d multi meter equipped with LDO oxygen sensor (Hach, Germany). Eggs were acclimated for ten days (freshwater, T = 5.0 °C) before the addition of microplastics. The embryos were monitored daily and dead eggs were immediately removed.

2.2. Microplastic exposure

Commercial microplastics (virgin pre-production pellets) of particle diameter ~ 3000 µm representing three polymer types: polyethylene (HDPE: ExxonMobil™ HTA 108, USA; density 0.961 g ml⁻¹, size: 3.22 ± 0.23 mm), polystyrene (BASF Polystyrol 143E, Germany; density 1.04 g ml⁻¹, size: 3.11 ± 0.09 mm, flammability, UL94 HB) and polyethylene terephthalate (PET; Polysciences, Inc., USA; density 1.370 g ml⁻¹, size: 3.08 ± 0.17 mm), representing the most widely manufactured, commonly used and abundant types of plastics in the marine and freshwater environments (Andrady and Neal, 2009; Sadri and Thompson, 2014; Horton et al., 2017a; Li et al., 2020; Plastics Europe, 2019) were used to obtain three different microplastics treatments hereafter referred to and abbreviated in the text as PE, PS and PET, respectively. There was one experimental setting (separate system) per treatment.

PE is considered one of the least hazardous polymers (Lithner et al., 2011) but is known to have a large affinity for a wide range of organic contaminants (Müller et al., 2001; Teuten et al., 2007; Rochman et al., 2013a, 2013b). PS is made from the styrene oligomers, which are considered harmful and able to migrate from plastic to different media (Hahladakis et al., 2018). The toxicity of PET is debatable: it usually contains less chemical additives than other polymers (Lithner et al., 2011) but its potential to leach endocrine disruptors is stressed (Sax, 2010). To reach the final concentration of 0.1% of sediment dry weight, 700 mg of each polymer type was added to the respective tanks. This concentration equivalent in all treatments to 2.8 mg l⁻¹ and corresponding to 22 PET, 25 PS and 28 PE pellets per tank (i.e. 0.055, 0.062

and 0.070 pellets l⁻¹ and 0.09, 0.10, 0.11 pellets per egg, respectively) lies within the lower range of microplastics concentrations considered environmentally relevant (0 – 1% plastic weight in sediment dry wt; Redondo-Hasselerharm et al., 2018) and is within the range of MPs numbers recorded in streams (e.g. up to 1 g kg⁻¹ or 4000 particles kg⁻¹ in sediments, Klein et al., 2015, or up to 303 particles m⁻³ in water and 80 particles kg⁻¹ in sediment, Dikareva and Simon, 2019). Similarly, 700 mg of ~3000 µm gravels (the same as on the incubators' bottom) were added to the control treatment (aquarium with embryos but without plastic pellets). Both microplastics and gravels used as the control had been kept in aerated water for 8 weeks before their addition to the respective incubators, in order to allow the development of microbial biofilm on their surface.

Due to differences in polymer densities, PET and PS pellets reached the bottoms of the incubators with the embryos on their surface immediately after addition, while lighter PE pellets floated freely on the water surface where they remained throughout the entire experiment. The water outflow pipe was covered by mesh that prevented the transfer of PE pellets to the system and their trapping on filters. Positions of the air stones and aeration intensity were adjusted in a way preventing pellets agitation and their excessive movement. PS and PET pellets remained on the bottom surface throughout the entire experiment and the water flow has not affected their initial position reached after their addition to the tanks.

Eggs incubation took place under dark conditions, while the natural photoperiod was applied after 100% hatching (on the 85th day). Overall, the fish were exposed to microplastics for 113 days, from fertilized eggs to mobile yolk-sack larvae. Due to endogenous feeding mode of the yolk-sack stage, larvae were not fed during the experiment. The temperature in each treatment was monitored continuously, while oxygen saturation was measured every two days. The water in each system was not exchanged during the whole duration of the experiment.

2.3. Data collection and preparation of samples

The numbers of dead eggs, hatched larvae and dead larvae were recorded daily. Dead eggs and larvae were immediately removed. After the mass hatching 30 larvae were randomly collected from each treatment on 3, 11, 18, 25 and 28 dph (day post hatching) and preserved in ethanol for morphometric analyses. At the end of the experiment, blood samples were taken by cutting off the tail of larvae for determination of geno- and cytotoxicity responses. Blood taken from the 15 larvae collected from each treatment was directly smeared on the microscopic slides. Dried blood smears were fixed in ethanol for 10 min and stained with 10% Giemsa solution in phosphate buffer pH = 6.8 for 40 min. Also 5 larvae from each treatment were collected, immediately frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored in -80 °C for the analysis of corticosteroid hormones concentrations in tissues.

2.4. Survival, hatching and growth rate determination

Based on the number of dead eggs, larvae, and hatched larvae recorded each day, the following developmental parameters were calculated: incubation period (the period after which all eggs hatched), hatching period (the interval between hatching of the first and last egg), hatching success (the survival of embryos) and survival of larvae. Since the fish growth is a function of temperature, some developmental parameters were expressed as a function of both, days of experiment (or days post hatching) and degree-days i.e., °C day (D°) (Ojanguren and Brana, 2003; Neuheimer and Taggart, 2007) to take into account any temperature-related variation among treatments. The wet weight (wet wt; ±0.0001 g) of each larvae and its standard length (SL; ± 0.01 mm) as well as length (L) and height (H) of yolk sack (±0.01 mm) were determined under stereoscopic microscope (SMZ 18, Nikon Japan). Since the yolk-sac in salmonids becomes elongated within a day

after hatching (Groot, 1996), it was assumed to be an ellipsoidal mass (prolate spheroid) and its volume was calculated using the equation given by Bagarinao (1986) and Heming and Buddington (1988):

$$V = 0.1667 \pi L H^2. \quad (1)$$

The growth rates (daily weight and length gain) and the daily rate of yolk-sack absorption were calculated.

2.5. Determination of tissue steroid compounds concentration

Each larvae were homogenized separately using 5 ml of homogenization buffer (8.5 mM MgCl₂, 3.13 mM KCl, 7.59 mM NaCl, 2.7 mM CaCl₂, 50 mM Tris/HCl, pH 7.4) per gram of tissue. Next, MTBE (tert-butyl methyl ether) was added, the sample was mixed for 1 min and the mixture centrifuged at 3000 ×g for 15 min at room temperature. The supernatant was transferred to a new glass vial and MTBE was allowed to evaporate to dryness in 45 °C. Upon evaporation, the dry residue of the eluate was dissolved in 100 µl of methanol and 5 µl of this solution was injected into the HPLC-ESI-MS/MS system. The elution was performed under a 10-min gradient. Testosterone-2,3,4-¹³C₃ and 4-Androstene-3,17-dione-2,3,4-¹³C₃ were used as internal standards. HPLC-ESI-MS/MS analysis was performed using a triple-quadrupole mass spectrometer (TSQ Vantage, Thermo Scientific) equipped with a ion electrospray source (ESI) coupled with a HPLC system (Thermo Scientific) using selected reaction monitoring (SRM) for detection in positive ion mode. All analytes were detected in SRM. The column used was Kinetex Phenyl-Hexyl 50 × 2.1 mm 1.7µ and Kinetex Biphenyl 50 × 1 mm 1.7µ (Phenomenex) regarding type of analyzed compounds. Buffers used for the HPLC gradient elution were: A: 0.1% formic acid in deionized water and B: 0.1% formic acid in methanol. Column equilibration was performed for 10 min. The total analysis time was 10 min. The flow rate was set at 0.2 ml min⁻¹, the column oven temperature at 25 °C, and the sample storage box temperature at 4 °C. The retention times ranged from 4 min 42 s for cortisol to 5 min 42 s for corticosterone. Detection of all steroids under the study was performed in positive ion mode using a triple-quadrupole mass analyzer. MS conditions and limits of detections are described in Table 1. Optimal MS/MS precursor-product transitions and voltages were used, following direct infusion of individual methanol solutions. Calibration curves were prepared based on matrix and plotted as the peak area ratio (standard/IS) versus amount of analytes. In the range of 0.03–100 ng g⁻¹ regression coefficients of all analytes were >0.99. All measurements were taken in triplicate, and the results were presented as mean values ± SD (n = 3).

2.6. Geno- and cytotoxicity analysis

The stained slides were analyzed under light microscopes Olympus BX51 (Tokyo, Japan) at final magnification of 1000×. Two thousands erythrocytes with intact cellular and nuclear membranes per

fish were evaluated using blind scoring on coded slides. Final results were expressed as the mean value (%) of sums of the analyzed individual lesions scored in 1000 cells per fish sampled from every study group. The frequencies of seven nuclear abnormalities were examined as markers of geno- or cytotoxicity in fish erythrocytes. Induction of micronuclei (MN), nuclear buds (NB), nuclear buds on filament (NBF) and blebbed nuclei (BL) erythrocytes were assessed as genotoxicity endpoints, while induction of fragmented apoptotic (FA), bi-nucleated (BN), and 8-shaped nuclei erythrocytes as cytotoxicity endpoints. Total genotoxicity (ΣGentox) levels were assessed as the sum of the frequencies of the detected genotoxicity (MN + NB + BL) endpoints. Morphological features of the nuclear abnormalities studied were identified using criteria described by Fenech et al. (2003) (the detailed description of these criteria was presented in previous study (Baršienė et al., 2014)).

2.7. Statistical analysis

Survival rates of embryos and larvae were compared among treatments using the comparisons of the Kaplan-Meier survival curves, which take into account the individuals that died during the experiment as well as individuals that were still alive at the end of the exposure. The percentage distribution of the hatched individuals (hatching rate) in each treatment was compared to their distribution in the control group using χ^2 -test. For each experimental treatment, the linear regression lines were fitted between wet wt, SL or yolk sac volume and the larvae age (dph). In case of wet wt only data for age up to 25 dph were described with linear regression. Regression lines (the homogeneity of regression slopes) were compared using analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) in order to compare the growth rates of larvae reared in MP treatments and in the control. Before this analysis: (1): boxplots were created to identify and remove outliers (>2 standard deviations from the mean); (2) the assumption on the normal distribution of the data was verified by the Shapiro-Wilk test; and (3) the homogeneity of observed residual variances in each group were tested using Levene's and Brown-Forsythe tests. Geno- and cytotoxicity data were first checked for normal distribution with Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests, and homogeneity of variances with Levene's and Bartlett's test. To test the significance of the differences in concentrations of geno- and cytotoxic endpoints as well as concentrations of corticosteroids in larvae in various treatments, the Kruskal-Wallis test at a confidence level of $\alpha = 95\%$ was used. All analyses were performed using STATISTICA software (10.0 Software, Inc. PA, USA).

3. Results

3.1. Survival, hatching and growth

The hatching success (survival of embryos) varied between 95.97% and 97.11% in PE and PS treatment, respectively (Fig. 1) while in the control treatment it amounted to 96.08%. No significant differences in hatching success were recorded among treatments (comparison of Kaplan-Meier survival curves, $\chi^2 = 1.16$, $p = 0.76$).

The survival of hatched larvae was also high in all treatments. It varied from 97.63% to 99.21% (in PS and PE treatment, respectively; Fig. 2) and did not differ significantly among experimental variants (comparison of Kaplan-Meier survival curves, $\chi^2 = 2.73$, $p = 0.44$). In control treatment it amounted to 98.68%.

The incubation period of sea trout embryos amounted to 85 days in all experimental treatments but the day of first hatching varied between 62nd and 75th day after fertilization, depending on the treatment (Table 2). The differences in hatching rate between individuals exposed to microplastics and the control ones were not statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 7.47$, $p = 0.98$; $\chi^2 = 20.63$, $p = 0.24$; $\chi^2 = 19.85$, $p = 0.28$ for PE, PET and PS respectively).

Table 1

Mass spectrometric conditions for analysis of analytes by positive ion electrospray ionization, LOD – limit of detection, Rt - retention time.

Analytes	MRM transition for monitoring		Collision energy (V)	LOD (ng g ⁻¹)	Rt (min)
	Precursor ion (m/z)	Product ion (m/z)			
Dehydrocorticosterone	345.2	121.3	24	0.03	5.31
		242.2			
Corticosterone	347.2	329.2	12	0.03	5.42
		121.3			
Cortisone	361.4	163.2	22	0.03	4.56

Fig. 1. Cumulative survival rate of *S. trutta* embryos during exposure to microplastics of different polymer types.

Fig. 2. Cumulative survival rate of *S. trutta* larvae during exposure to microplastics of different polymer types.

The temperature averaged for 113 days of experiment varied between 5.16 ± 0.36 in PS treatment and 5.40 ± 0.60 in the control. The oxygen saturation never fell below 100% (Table 2).

The growth rate of *S. trutta* larvae expressed by changes in wet weight varied between $0.229 \text{ mg day}^{-1}$ in larvae exposed to PS to $0.544 \text{ mg day}^{-1}$ in the control treatment. No significant differences in weight gain between 3 and 25 dph were observed in fish exposed to all microplastic types compared to the non-exposed individuals (Fig. 3; ANCOVA slope, $F(1,234) = 0.02, p = 0.88$; $F(1,234) = 2.48, p = 0.12$; $F(1,228) = 3.26, p = 0.07$ respectively for PE, PET and PS).

Table 2

The length of the incubation and hatching period of *S. trutta* during 113 days of exposure to microplastics of different polymer types.

	Control	PET	PS	PE
T (°C)	5.40 ± 0.60	5.24 ± 0.56	5.16 ± 0.36	5.35 ± 0.56
O ₂ (mg l ⁻¹)	12.78 ± 0.30	12.93 ± 0.27	12.92 ± 0.19	12.87 ± 0.20
First hatching (days)	69	62	69	75
First hatching (D°)	427	374	409	446
Hatching period (days)	17	24	17	11
Hatching period (D°)	85	120	82	52
Time to hatch > 90% (days)	78	82	82	80
Time to hatch > 90% (D°)	474	478	476	472
Incubation period (days)	85	85	85	85
Incubation period (D°)	511	494	491	498

Fig. 3. Changes in wet weight of larval *S. trutta* during exposure to microplastics of different polymer types. Open circles represent non-outlier data for all individuals, closed squares - mean \pm SD ($n = 24-35$).

The daily length gain varied between $0.132 \text{ mm day}^{-1}$ in the control to $0.161 \text{ mm day}^{-1}$ in PET treatment, while the daily yolk sack absorption was lowest in the control treatment ($0.753 \mu\text{m}^3 \text{ day}^{-1}$) and highest in PS-exposed larvae ($0.900 \text{ mm}^3 \text{ day}^{-1}$). Similarly to weight gain, between 3 and 28 dph, no effect of microplastics was recorded on either length gain (Fig. 4; ANCOVA slope, $F(1,286) = 3.53, p = 0.06$; $F(1,287) = 2.58, p = 0.11$; $F(1,280) = 0.40, p = 0.52$ respectively for PE, PET and PS) or the yolk sacks absorption rate (Fig. 5; ANCOVA slope, $F(1,285) = 0.09, p = 0.77$; $F(1,287) = 0.33, p = 0.33$; $F(1,283) = 1.03, p = 0.31$ respectively for PE, PET and PS). Hatched larvae were non-feeding.

Fig. 4. Changes in standard length of larval *S. trutta* during exposure to microplastics of different polymer types. Open circles represent non-outlier data for all individuals, closed squares - mean \pm SD ($n = 24-35$).

Fig. 5. Changes in yolk sack volume of larval *S. trutta* during exposure to microplastics of different polymer types. Open circles represent non-outlier data for all individuals, closed squares - mean \pm SD ($n = 24-35$).

3.2. Determination of tissue steroid compounds concentration

The mean concentrations of both, corticosterone and its biologically inactive metabolite - dehydrocorticosterone, were elevated compared to the control concentrations, especially in PE-treated larvae (Fig. 6A). The differences were, however, not statistically significant (Kruskal-Wallis test, $H = 1.84$, $p = 0.60$; $H = 6.72$, $p = 0.08$). Cortisone concentrations were lower in larvae exposed to all MPs types than in the control, but the differences were also not significant (Kruskal-Wallis test, $H = 6.55$, $p = 0.08$) (Fig. 6B). The detectable amount of cortisol was recorded only in individuals exposed to PS (Fig. 6B).

3.3. Geno- and cytotoxic effects

The exposure to PS and PET induced significant formation of MN (Kruskal-Wallis test, $H = 19.01$, 3 d.f., $p = 0.003$) and BL ($H = 11.97$, 3 d.f., $p = 0.0075$) in *S. trutta* erythrocytes compared to the control group ($p = 0.0005$, $p = 0.023$ and $p = 0.019$, $p = 0.046$, respectively). All MPs treatments resulted in a significantly elevated frequencies of NB (Kruskal-Wallis test, $H = 21.16$, 3 d.f., $p = 0.0001$) compared to the control group ($p = 0.0001$, $p = 0.044$, $p = 0.013$) (Fig. 7A). Total genotoxicity (Σ Gentox) was significantly (Kruskal-Wallis test, $H = 29.27$, 3 d.f., $p < 0.0001$) higher in all treatments compared to the control ($p < 0.0001$, $p = 0.034$ and $p = 0.0004$, respectively). Σ Gentox values varied from 1.83‰ to 2.93‰ in MPs treated groups with the lowest level of total genotoxicity detected in PE-exposed group (Fig. 7B).

8-Shaped nuclei erythrocytes was the only one cytotoxicity endpoint detected in MPs-exposed groups. The frequencies of 8-shaped nuclei erythrocytes were low, while induction of fragmented apoptotic and BN erythrocytes were not observed at all. 8-shaped nuclei frequencies varied from 0.07‰ in PE group to 0.33‰ in PS-exposed group (0.03‰ in control group). Frequencies of detected cytotoxicity endpoint did not show any significant (Kruskal-Wallis test, $p > 0.05$) changes in the MPs treatment groups compared to the control.

Fig. 6. Mean \pm SD ($n_{\text{control}} = 3$, $n_{\text{PE, PET, PS}} = 5$) concentrations of whole-body corticosteroids in *S. trutta* after 113-day exposure to microplastics of different polymer types. A - dehydrocorticosterone and corticosterone, B - cortisone and cortisol.

Fig. 7. Frequencies of genotoxicity endpoints (micronuclei (MN), nuclear buds (NB), blebbed (BL) nuclei cells (A) and total genotoxicity (Σ Gentox) levels induced in erythrocytes (B) of *S. trutta* after 113-day exposure to microplastics of different polymer types. Asterisks (*) denote significant differences from the control group, mean \pm SEM ($n = 15$).

4. Discussion

The embryo-larval and early juvenile life stages in fish life-cycle are considered to be particularly vulnerable to pollution due to their limited capacity to regulate their internal environment and to avoid stressors. On the other hand, embryos are known of having high levels of cellular defenses already present in the egg before fertilization and adaptive responses to the environment during their development that allow to either buffer stress or produce alternative developmental phenotypes (Hamdoun and Epel, 2007).

The chronic exposure of *S. trutta* embryos and larvae to microplastics in our experiment has not affected hatching, growth and survival of these developmental stages. The survival of *S. trutta* embryos was high (>90%) in all experimental treatments indicating that any type of polymer added did not cause their mortality or did not negatively affect embryos development and the hatching success, which was as high as 96–97%. Chronic exposure to MPs also did not affect survival of sea trout hatched larvae (97–99%) which was significantly higher than observed for this species reared in laboratory conditions at similar temperature (~40–60% depending on the developmental stage; Ojanguren and Brana, 2003). It seems therefore, that overall experimental conditions applied in our study were optimal for the development of sea trout early life stages. Similarly, the survival rates of embryos and larvae of the zebrafish *D. rerio* were not affected by exposure to various types and concentrations of micro- or nanoplastics, although negative effects, such as reduced growth, oxidative stress, inhibited locomotion (Chen et al., 2017), changes in gene expression (Chen et al., 2017; LeMoine et al., 2018) or decreased heart rate and accumulation of nanoparticles in various internal organs (Pitt et al., 2018) were observed. Increased mortality of fish juveniles and adults was previously recorded but only after their exposure to high, environmentally unrealistic concentrations of MPs small enough to be ingested, or after direct dietary exposure (Mazurais et al., 2015; Lei et al., 2018; Naidoo and Glassom, 2019).

Hatching rate of *S. trutta* in our study has not varied among MPs treatments, though some variation in first and last hatching, and thus the hatching period (the interval between the hatching of the first and last egg) has been observed. Both the earliest first hatching and the longest hatching period (24 days) were recorded in the PET treatment, while in PE treatment hatching took only 11 days. These differences were, however, attributed to single embryos (in total, $\leq 1\%$ of all individuals) whereas the period of mass hatching was similar in all treatments, i.e. took place between 460 and 480 degree days. Inter-individual variability in hatching period typical for salmonids may be attributed to the genetic variation that substantially affects the developmental processes (Ferguson et al., 1985; Hutchings, 2011). The incubation period, i.e., the period after which all eggs hatched, equivalent to 85 days in all our experimental treatments, is typical for *S. trutta* incubated at similar temperature (~ 5.4 °C; Embury, 1934). Similarly to our results, no changes in hatching rate were observed in *D. rerio* reared with much smaller MPs (PE, 10–45 μm , 20 mg l^{-1} , LeMoine et al., 2018), or nanoparticles (PS, 51 nm, 0.1–10 ppm, Pitt et al., 2018), or in *Oryzias melastigma* exposed to PE MPs (1–63 μm , up to 10 mg l^{-1}), though the same MPs spiked with benzophenone-3, a common plastic stabilizer, were responsible for decreased hatching rate, survival of embryos and the time to hatch (Beiras et al., 2018).

Results of our study do not indicate that exposure to any MPs type affected rates of larvae growth expressed by changes in body length or weight. This is in line with other observations performed on larval stages of *D. labrax* and *D. rerio* (Mazurais et al., 2015; Karami et al., 2017; LeMoine et al., 2018) or juvenile *Sparus aurata* (Jovanović et al., 2018) although it must be stressed that larvae in these experiments ingested and accumulated microplastics in gastro-intestinal tracts. One may hypothesize that reduced growth of an organism exposed to MPs can be a consequence of either redirecting energy dedicated for growth into the microplastics and/or associated pollutants excretion processes, or a result of reduced feeding due to false satiation. Reduced growth rates were for instance found in juvenile *Ambassis dussumieri* exposed to both virgin and potentially polluted (collected from the harbor) microplastics (Naidoo and Glassom, 2019) or in zebrafish *D. rerio* after exposure to nanoparticles (Chen et al., 2017).

Also the absorption rate of yolk-sacks of larval *S. trutta* has not varied significantly among various experimental treatments. Unfortunately, although several studies investigated the effect of MPs on fish early life stages, the absorption rate of yolk sack has never been studied. Changes in yolk sack utilization rate are typical stress response in larval fish and it is well documented that both retarded and faster yolk sac absorption may have serious consequences for further growth and first feeding of salmonid larvae (Nelson, 1982; Hansen, 1985; Fey et al., 2019a). Retarded yolk-sack absorption rates were observed in larvae exposed to e.g., reduced pH, adverse salinity, low oxygen concentration or various pollutants (Heming and Buddington, 1988 and references therein), while increased temperature, astro-turf artificial substrate, magnetic and electromagnetic fields accelerated this process (Hansen, 1985; Hardy and Litvak, 2004; Fey et al., 2019a, 2019b).

The majority of experimental studies (including many of those cited above) focused on investigation of MPs impacts on the biota, use experimental settings that allow ingestion of MPs by tested organisms, thus conclusions drawn from these experiments are usually based on effects of MPs intake. We have used non-ingestion related type of exposure. Although yolk sac larvae feed endogenously they are able to ingest small particles. However, plastic pellets used in this study were too large to be ingested by larvae at this stage of their development. To our best knowledge only two studies aimed to investigate effects of microplastics on the survival and development of early life stages of aquatic organisms and were not related to microplastics ingestion or their physical penetration through the body membranes of tested organisms. Nobre et al. (2015) observed that leachates from virgin PE granules and from various plastic pellets collected from the beach caused abnormal development of embryos of sea urchin *Lytechinus*

variegatus. Similar results were obtained by Gandara e Silva et al. (2016) who exposed the embryos of mussel *Perna perna* to virgin polypropylene particles as well as to beached pellets and found that both types of MPs caused abnormal embryos development or death after 48-hour exposure, thus indicating severe and acute toxicity of leachates from MPs. It should be kept in mind, however, that very high MPs concentrations, corresponding to 50–250 ml l^{-1} , were applied in both mentioned experiments, which in addition were performed in small vessels (volume of 0.008–1 l) thus creating conditions being far from the natural. Nevertheless, the negative effects observed in the aforementioned studies were attributed to the most common plastic additives or contaminants adsorbed from the environment.

Corticosteroid hormones, mainly cortisol, are the most common and frequently used bioindicator of stress in fish. Cortisol levels, typically measured in blood samples, usually experience increase in response to acute stress: 10–100 fold in adult fish (Barton and Iwama, 1991) and 2–4 fold in larval salmonids (Pottinger and Mosuwe, 1994; Barry et al., 1995a, 1995b). The method of measuring whole-body levels of corticosteroids used in the present study is commonly used in small or larval fish (Barry et al., 1995a, 1995b; Pottinger and Mosuwe, 1994; Pottinger et al., 2016) but since corticosteroids concentrations are measured by this method in all body compartments their values are incomparable with those obtained from blood samples. Our results revealed detectable cortisol concentrations only in fish exposed to PS. These concentrations were low, but in control larvae as well as those exposed to other polymers they were below the detection limit. These data are difficult to interpret, but since the mean cortisol concentration in PS-exposed fish was not significantly higher than in the control group (concentrations below the detection limit), one might conclude that the hypothalamus-pituitary-interrenal (HPI) axis has not been stimulated by the exposure to MPs. The HPI axis in salmonids is functionally integrated and responsive to stress approximately 2 weeks after hatching (Barry et al., 1995a, 1995b), thus more pronounced response to environmental stress might have been expected in our experiment. To the best of our knowledge, changes in concentrations of corticosteroid hormones have not been previously investigated in fish exposed to microplastics. The knowledge on endocrine responses after exposure to potential plastic additives is also very limited. Elevated cortisol levels or disruptions of HPI axis were observed in fish after exposure to phthalate plasticizers or nonylphenols (Teles et al., 2005; Lerner et al., 2007; Revathy and Chitra, 2019). Cortisol is the main and physiologically most important end product of HPI axis in teleost fish, however cortisone and corticosterone have also been previously detected in the blood of salmonids (Nandi and Bern, 1960; Idler and Truscott, 1972; Sandor, 1979; Pottinger and Moran, 1993; Sangalang and Uthe, 1994). They may be produced by fish in response to stress, however this matter especially in relation to corticosterone which is the primary stress hormone in many terrestrial animals (Wendelaar Bonga, 1997), is still poorly studied (Schreck and Tort, 2016). We have not observed significantly elevated concentrations of corticosterone in *S. trutta* larvae after exposure to all polymer types compared to the control treatment but high inter-individual variability was observed. The interpretation of these results is, however difficult due to a lack of comparable data. Chronically elevated cortisol levels are usually accompanied by suppression of immune functions and reduction in growth rate (Barton and Iwama, 1991; Wendelaar Bonga, 1997). The fact that any noticeable changes in larvae weight or length were not observed in *S. trutta* exposed to MPs might confirm the assumption that the HPI axis was not stimulated during exposure to microplastics. In addition, we must stress that our results are based on a limited number of samples thus must be treated with due caution and, as such, their interpretation is additionally hampered.

MN assay quantifies chromosomal damage through the evaluation of the formation of micronuclei and other NAs within cells. MN and associated NAs such as nuclear buds (NB) and blebbed (BL) nuclei cells are biomarkers of gene amplification, elimination of amplified DNA, DNA

repair complexes and possibly excess chromosomes from aneuploid cells (Serrano-García and Montero-Montoya, 2001; Fenech et al., 2011, 2016). In the present study, MN, NB and BL as proven indicators of genotoxic damage increased significantly in *S. trutta* exposed to MPs. The level of total genotoxicity (\sum Gentox) in fish erythrocytes increased in the following sequence: PS > PET > PE. Genotoxic and cytotoxic effects of MPs on aquatic organisms are insufficiently documented and the mechanism underlying MPs genotoxic activity has not been elucidated. Increased DNA breaks were detected in larvae and juveniles of fish *Oryzias latipes* after 15–30 days of dietary exposure (0.01–0.1% of food) to environmental microplastics (Pannetier et al., 2020). Genotoxic effects (DNA strand breaks, MN frequency or nuclear alterations) of virgin and contaminated PE and PS MPs were investigated in invertebrates: *Mytilus galloprovincialis* (Avio et al., 2015) and PS-MPs in *Scrobicularia plana* (Ribeiro et al., 2017), indicating various forms of genotoxicity in haemocytes. It was hypothesized that DNA strand breaks as the first form of damage are caused by the increased formation of ROS in response to MPs. Higher PS-induced prooxidant challenge compared to other MPs can result in irreversible loss of DNA integrity (nuclear abnormalities) leading to increased frequency of micronuclei (Avio et al., 2015). Moreover, cytogenetic potential of nano- and micro-sized PS-MPs have been evaluated in higher plant *Vicia faba* (Jiang et al., 2019) and *Allium cepa* (Maity et al., 2020), and oxidative damage was also emphasized. In the case of MPs cytotoxicity to aquatic organisms almost no data has been reported to date and only few human cell studies have been performed to determine the cytotoxic effects of nanoplastics. Results herein reported show that exposure to MPs did not induce significant cytotoxic effects in fish. The lack of nanosized PS cytotoxicity effects was observed in human cell lines (Cortés et al., 2020), while in several studies (Hwang et al., 2019; Schirinzì et al., 2017) MPs (PP and PE, PS) have been reported to be slightly cytotoxic to human cells.

Adverse effects of MPs observed in our experiment i.e., formation of genotoxicity endpoints and increased levels of total genotoxicity or detectable levels of cortisol were observed in treatments with PS and/or PET (Figs. 6, 7). The common feature of these two polymers is their higher density compared to the water and PE pellets, which in our experiment led to different ways of exposure of sea trout embryos and newly hatched larvae to these different MPs types. PS and PET pellets were incubated at the bottom - in close proximity to embryos, in some cases even in a direct contact, while PE pellets remained on the water surface throughout the entire experiment. The studies of Nobre et al. (2015) and Gandara e Silva et al. (2016) stressed out that the different methodological approach i.e., shape of the experimental vessel and thus the proximity of plastic particles to embryos, may significantly modulate the toxicity of pollutants leaching from MPs. Also in our experiment, embryos and larvae laying in the close proximity to pellets (PS, PET) might have been more vulnerable to transport of leachates than those exposed to PE pellets which remained on the water surface throughout the entire experiment. Leachates may contain specific unpolymerized residual monomers or any additive chemical ingredients usually not bound to the polymer matrix, that can migrate off the plastic (Lithner et al., 2011). Unfortunately, we have not studied leachates in detail but according to our knowledge, PS pellets used in our experiment exhibited higher contents of several PAHs compared to PE. For instance, concentration of phenanthrene was one order of magnitude higher in PS pellets compared to PE (20.3 vs. 2.7 ng g⁻¹, Nguyen and Scales, 2019). PAHs are formed usually during the manufacture of polystyrene (Rochman et al., 2013c). In addition, PS products have been shown to contain harmful styrene oligomers, which are generated as by-products in the process of polymerization (Halden, 2010; Lithner et al., 2011) and can migrate from plastic to various media (Hahladakis et al., 2018). Despite the fact that PET is one of the most commonly used polymers and one of the most common types of MPs in aquatic ecosystems, its potential toxicity is still under debate. PET requires less additives (e.g. plasticizers) and degrades faster than other polymers

(Lithner et al., 2011) but may contain additives being potential endocrine disruptors (toxic phthalates, antimony or nonylphenols) that may leach and negatively affect biota (Wagner and Oehlmann, 2009; Sax, 2010 and references therein). PE is ranked as one of least hazardous polymers (Lithner et al., 2011) but its potential hazard is related to its low crystallinity, thus ability to accumulate more contaminants from the environment and higher desorption rates than other polymers such as PVC, PET or PS (Rochman et al., 2013b; Teuten et al., 2009). In addition, polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs) and hexabromocyclododecanes (HBCDDs) are often added to plastic pellets as the flame retardants (Teuten et al., 2009; Engler, 2012). Hence, plastic debris may be a source of these compounds in aquatic environments and in organisms (Rochman et al., 2014b; Hermabessiere et al., 2017) especially that flame retardants have high affinity to organic matter and tissues (Rochman et al., 2014b). We have determined their concentrations in water collected from each experimental tank at the end of the experiment, but these concentrations were below the limit of quantification (LOQ = 2.5 ng ml⁻¹). Also, due to insufficient fat content, the analysis of PBDE and HBCDDs in larvae tissues was unsuccessful (data not shown).

According to Lithner et al. (2011) even several thousand different additives exist for plastic polymers and lot of them may negatively affect the biota (Halden, 2010; Hermabessiere et al., 2017; Hahladakis et al., 2018). Unfortunately, due to industry policies, no additional information about their types and concentrations is available from producers. Also in experimental studies aimed to investigate the effects of plastics and their leachates on the biota the chemical compounds are usually not being identified and thus the discussions on the potential impacts of associated pollutants are often rather speculative (i.e., based on the typical chemical composition of studied polymers and/or common additives, or contaminants present in the environment, e.g. Lithner et al., 2012; Nobre et al., 2015; Pedà et al., 2016). Since some pollutants were reported to leach and affect the biota even after 24 h of exposure to plastic (Nobre et al., 2015; León et al., 2019), we may suggest that long incubation time applied in our experiment (113 days) was sufficient to release by MPs some kind of additives in concentrations adequate to induce adverse effects such as increased genotoxicity in larvae. However, without information on the concentrations of particular chemical compounds in pellets and their diffusion coefficients above considerations are mainly speculative.

The main advantage of our approach to the experiment, which is fundamentally different from the majority of experimental studies dedicated to the research on the effect of MPs on fauna, is application of the system with a large water capacity and water flow that aimed to imitate the natural environment. The latter seems to be crucial when designing the experimental system for wild and rather poorly cultivatable species such as *S. trutta*. In addition, our experiment has been run for almost 4 months, thus the exposure of embryos and larvae to plastic pellets can be classified as chronic. On the other hand, the use of one setting per treatment group and thus a lack of more replicates is a weak point of our experimental design, which must be taken into account when interpreting the results. Based on these results, we may conclude that long term exposure to relatively large microplastics of three different polymer types does not affect the basic processes, crucial for the population recruitment, such as hatching, growth, development and survival of early life stages of *S. trutta*. Adverse effects are manifested, however, in induction of genotoxic changes. Also concentrations of some corticosteroid stress hormones were elevated but due to high inter-individual variability their interpretation is difficult. In contrast to the majority of studies, our investigation was not based on dietary exposure to MPs thus our results may be related mainly the hazardous nature of MPs itself (chemical composition of polymers) and/or the potential chemical additives, which were, however, not studied here in detail. Also the polymer density might modulate the availability of potential leachates to sessile live stage: heavier polymers reach the bottom faster than lighter ones thus benthic life stages are more vulnerable to their toxic

effects. Our results suggest that polystyrene is the most toxic among the studied polymers, however it is not unequivocal whether this effect is related to its basic composition e.g., polymerization impurities or to potential additives. Therefore the presence and fate of the chemical additives to virgin MPs in the aquatic environments and their effects on organisms should be a subject to further detailed investigations, especially since the information on additives applied in MP granules is usually not provided by producers. Since the present study shows that even low concentrations of MPs may induce a negative response in aquatic organisms, more research on the environmentally relevant concentrations is needed.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Magdalena Jakubowska: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Visualization, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. **Marcin Białowas:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing - review & editing. **Milda Stankevičiūtė:** Investigation, Data curation, Visualization, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. **Agnieszka Chomiczewska:** Investigation, Validation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. **Janina Pażusienė:** Investigation, Data curation, Visualization. **Karolina Jonko-Sobuś:** Investigation, Validation, Writing - original draft. **Anna Hallmann:** Investigation, Validation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. **Barbara Urban-Malinga:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing, Resources, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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